

Reactive Arthritis After *Enterococcus faecalis* Catheter-Associated Urinary Tract Infection

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Abstract—Reactive arthritis (ReA) is a sterile inflammatory arthritis typically triggered by gastrointestinal or genitourinary infections, with common pathogens including *Chlamydia trachomatis* and *Salmonella*. Though rare, urinary tract infections (UTIs) caused by *Enterococcus faecalis* can also trigger ReA. Diagnosis is clinical, established through a recent infection history and characteristic joint involvement. We present a 61-year-old female with a history of depression and ADHD, who was found in a state of self-neglect and diagnosed with failure to thrive. During hospitalization, she developed symptoms of a UTI, and urine culture grew *Enterococcus faecalis*. Patient's symptoms subsequently evolved to include joint stiffness, ocular discharge, and nasal congestion, she was diagnosed with reactive arthritis, likely triggered by her prolonged UTI. The patient was treated and showed improvement throughout her admission. This case highlights the importance of considering reactive arthritis in patients with atypical infectious triggers such as *Enterococcus faecalis* UTI, especially in the context of prolonged catheterization and persistent infection. Early recognition and appropriate management can improve outcomes. Further research is needed to better characterize the spectrum of pathogens implicated in ReA and to optimize diagnostic and therapeutic strategies. (*Abstract*)

Keywords—*Reactive arthritis, Enterococcus faecalis, Urinary tract infection, Catheter-associated infection, Sterile arthritis (key words)*

I. INTRODUCTION

Reactive arthritis is a sterile inflammatory arthritis that typically develops after an extra-articular infection, most commonly involving the gastrointestinal or genitourinary tracts [1]. It classically occurs following infections with *Chlamydia trachomatis*, *Salmonella*, *Shigella*, *Yersinia*, and *Campylobacter* species [2,3]. The diagnosis of reactive arthritis is primarily clinical, based on the presence of an

asymmetric oligoarthritis, often involving the lower extremities, in the setting of a recent infection, along with supportive laboratory findings and the exclusion of alternative causes such as septic arthritis, crystal arthropathies, and autoimmune diseases [4]. While *Chlamydia*-associated urethritis is a well-established trigger, reports of urinary tract infections (UTIs) leading to reactive arthritis are rare. In particular, *Enterococcus* species, which are common uropathogens, have only infrequently been implicated in the pathogenesis of reactive arthritis [5]. Given the rarity of UTI-associated cases and the diagnostic challenge they pose in distinguishing reactive arthritis from other infectious and inflammatory arthritides, careful clinical evaluation is crucial. Here, we report a case of reactive arthritis following a UTI caused by *Enterococcus* and discuss the important differential diagnoses to consider when approaching a patient with suspected reactive arthritis.

II. CASE REPORT

A. Case Presentation

A 61-year-old female with a history of depression, attention-deficit/hyperactivity disorder (ADHD), appendectomy, and hysterectomy presented to the emergency department after being found on the floor of her home by her brother, soiled in urine and feces. She reported a history of progressively worsening self-neglect over the past year, including cessation of bathing, dental hygiene, intermittent eating, and medication nonadherence. At presentation, she complained of lower abdominal pain and bloating. Physical examination was unremarkable. Laboratory evaluation revealed a lactate level of 5.7 mmol/L. A CT scan of the abdomen and pelvis

demonstrated mild bilateral hydronephrosis, likely secondary to a markedly distended bladder, as well as increased stool burden and rectal wall thickening suggestive of proctitis. Initial urinalysis was unremarkable. Bladder scan revealed 1250 mL of retained urine, and a Foley catheter was placed. The patient was diagnosed with failure to thrive secondary to depression and admitted for medical and psychiatric management.

B. Hospital Course

The patient's hospital course was prolonged due to placement challenges and complicated by persistent urinary retention, necessitating Foley catheterization from hospital day 2 through day 23. Psychiatry consultation during admission resulted in a new diagnosis of bipolar I disorder, for which she was started on aripiprazole. On hospital day 6, the patient developed cloudy urine and initial urinalysis revealed fewer than 100,000 colonies of *Enterococcus faecalis*, and no antibiotics were initiated.

On day 28, the patient developed dysuria, urinary urgency, and malodorous, cloudy urine. A urinalysis was performed and revealed a first positive urine culture with significant leukocyte esterase and pyuria (>182 WBCs/hpf), and urine culture grew >100,000 CFU/mL of *Enterococcus faecalis*, susceptible to ampicillin, ciprofloxacin, nitrofurantoin, and vancomycin, but resistant to cephalosporins and tetracycline. A diagnosis of catheter-associated urinary tract infection (CAUTI) was made, and intravenous ceftriaxone was initially started, then switched to ciprofloxacin based on susceptibility results.

On hospital day 29, the patient developed bilateral yellow ocular discharge and nasal congestion. Despite initial treatment with erythromycin eye ointment, her ocular symptoms worsened. Simultaneously, she developed new-onset joint stiffness involving both wrists and hands (right greater than left), and the right knee. Ophthalmology consultation led to initiation of prednisone 1% eyedrops for symptom control and Polytrim to prevent secondary bacterial infection.

Given her constellation of ocular, articular, and genitourinary symptoms, serologic testing for *Chlamydia pneumoniae* and *Chlamydia trachomatis* was pursued. Testing revealed positive *C. pneumoniae* IgG at 1:64 with negative IgM, and negative *C. trachomatis* IgG and IgM. Parvovirus B19 IgG was positive, consistent with prior exposure, while IgM was negative. HLA-B27 testing was not performed during the admission. Over the following two days, the patient's symptoms gradually improved, and she was discharged home after 33 days of hospitalization.

III. DISCUSSION

Reactive arthritis is a well-recognized sterile inflammatory arthritis triggered by infections, most commonly gastrointestinal or genitourinary in origin. The pathogenesis involves an aberrant immune response to microbial antigens in genetically susceptible individuals, often associated with HLA-B27 positivity, although this is not universal. While *Chlamydia trachomatis* and enteric bacteria such as *Salmonella* and *Shigella* are the most common triggers, a growing body of literature has identified rare and emerging

pathogens, including *Enterococcus* species, as potential triggers [6,7].

This case illustrates a rare but important clinical scenario of reactive arthritis following a prolonged *Enterococcus faecalis* urinary tract infection complicated by catheterization. The diagnosis was supported by the temporal relationship between infection and onset of arthritis and conjunctivitis, the exclusion of septic arthritis and other mimics, and the clinical improvement with treatment of the underlying infection and symptomatic management. Septic arthritis was deemed unlikely due to the absence of fever, localized erythema, or a systemic inflammatory response. Crystal arthropathies were not supported by imaging, and autoimmune markers were not indicative of an inflammatory arthropathy. The temporal relationship to UTI onset and constellation of ocular, joint, and urinary symptoms supported the diagnosis of reactive arthritis

The rarity of *Enterococcus*-associated reactive arthritis may be due to under-recognition or under-reporting, as *Enterococcus* is a common uropathogen, especially in catheterized patients. The clinical presentation of reactive arthritis typically includes asymmetric oligoarthritis predominantly affecting the lower extremities, conjunctivitis or uveitis, and urethritis or cervicitis, although presentations can be variable. The diagnosis remains clinical, supported by laboratory and microbiologic evidence of preceding infection, and exclusion of other causes such as septic arthritis, crystal arthropathies, and autoimmune diseases [7,8]. Although HLA-B27 positivity is associated with increased susceptibility to reactive arthritis, many cases occur in HLA-B27-negative individuals [1,6]. In this case, testing was not performed during admission but would have added value in characterizing immune predisposition.

Treatment of reactive arthritis is primarily symptomatic, including nonsteroidal anti-inflammatory drugs (NSAIDs), corticosteroids, and physical therapy. Antibiotic therapy is indicated for the underlying infection, particularly in *Chlamydia*-induced reactive arthritis, although the benefit of antibiotics in enteric or other bacterial triggers is less clear. In this patient, targeted antibiotic therapy for *Enterococcus faecalis* UTI was administered, alongside topical corticosteroids for ocular symptoms and supportive care for arthritis [1,7,9].

This case underscores the importance of considering reactive arthritis in patients with persistent or complicated UTIs, especially with unusual pathogens and prolonged catheterization. Early recognition can prevent unnecessary investigations and guide appropriate management. Further research is warranted to better define the epidemiology, pathogenesis, and optimal treatment strategies for reactive arthritis triggered by rare pathogens such as *Enterococcus*.

IV. CONCLUSION

Reactive arthritis should be considered in the differential diagnosis of patients presenting with arthritis and extra-articular manifestations following urinary tract infections,

including those caused by *Enterococcus faecalis*. Although rare, *Enterococcus*-associated reactive arthritis represents an important clinical entity, particularly in patients with prolonged catheterization and persistent infection. Diagnosis remains clinical, supported by microbiologic evidence and exclusion of other causes. Management includes treatment of the underlying infection and symptomatic therapy. Increased awareness and reporting of such cases will enhance understanding and improve patient outcomes.

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